

Dataset for article

Zalachoras I, Ramos-Fernández E, Hollis F, Trovo L, Rodrigues J, Strasser A, Zanoletti O, Steiner P, Preitner N, Xin L, Astori S, Sandi C. Glutathione in the nucleus accumbens regulates motivation to exert reward-incentivized effort. *Elife*. 2022 Nov 8;11:e77791. doi: 10.7554/eLife.77791. PMID: 36345724; PMCID: PMC9642999.

File name

elife-77791-fig1-data1-v1.xlsx
elife-77791-fig2-data1-v1.xlsx
elife-77791-fig3-data1-v1.xlsx
elife-77791-fig4-data1-v1.xlsx
elife-77791-fig5-data1-v1.xlsx

File type

xlsx, Excel file
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Description:

Each file contains numeric data used to generate the graphs in the main and supplementary figures of the paper. Excel sheets are labeled to correspond to the respective figure panels.